

CAUSES OF HYPODYNAMY - THE IMPORTANCE OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND SPORTS IN FIGHTING AGAINST IT.

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Annotation: In this article, the basic information about how people get various diseases due to inactivity or lack of movement and how important physical activities are for our health is presented in a systematic order. This article serves as one of the most important resources for professionals in the field to guide people suffering from excess weight gained due to inactivity, poor diet, and lack of oxygen in the body.

Key words: Hypodynamia, obesity, intensive, inactivity, hygienic exercises, oxygen, nutrition, metabolism, organism, innovative, individual.

We often use the phrase in marriage that life is always action, and it really is. All living organisms, especially animals, are in constant motion. Animals find food for themselves and

it is necessary to be active in order to avoid danger. Movement is one of the important characteristics of a living organism. Accordingly, the human being has always had to engage in active muscle activity during its evolutionary formation. Intensive muscle activity is a necessary condition for living. Maintaining physical activity at the optimal level is necessary for the normal passage of all life processes.

"Nature does not recognize the cessation of movement and punishes inaction," said Goethe. In the conditions of scientific and technical progress, people have drastically reduced physical activity. However, it is an important stimulant in the process of metabolism.

In today's rapidly developing era, as people's intellectual capacity increases, so do their discoveries. The discoveries themselves are the basis for the creation of other innovative projects. Regardless of the purpose of the discovery, it leads to the

benefits of people, that is, to the relief of their hard work. This is definitely good. But as there are two sides of a coin, the inventions that are being created, while increasing labor productivity by easing the burdens of people, bring many diseases to themselves. In particular, as we said above, discoveries that relieve people's pain reduce their movement activity and become the basis for the emergence of the disease called hypodynamia (low mobility, weakness). As a result of lack of mobility, overweight (obesity) in a person, overweight itself causes changes in the cardiovascular system (myocardial dystrophy, coronary blood circulation disorders, blood circulation disorders in the brain and lower parts), the respiratory system (a decrease in the temperature of the breath causes the diaphragm due to lack of movement), diseases of the digestive system (hypersecretion of gastric juice), locomotor apparatus (arthrosis due to increased load on the joints and metabolic disorders), diabetes (pancreatic dysfunction, increased blood sugar) causes. This causes an increase in the number of deaths.

The number of urban residents has been increasing over the last 10-15 years in the developed (USA, Germany) and developing countries, especially in Uzbekistan. As a result, residents of the city live in multi-storey apartments. Urban residents are less active than rural residents. Because of this, many thousands of people living in cities suffer from hypodynamia. When we looked at statistical data, we were sure that city residents suffer from this disease more than rural residents. There are various reasons for being less active, for example, in our simple life, we can remotely control the air conditioner, TV, and even the lights, if we need to do laundry, we wash it in the car, and if we need to sweep the house, we use a vacuum cleaner. Even more interesting, there are opportunities to clean the carpet without removing it from its place. We can send a message to a neighbor by phone without leaving the house. It can be seen that the easy performance of each of our tasks is connected with the development of technology.

Technical progress is not only making our work easier, but also saving our time. In return for this saved time, it is advisable to engage in some physical activity,

sports, not limited to work activities that can be done only by sleeping, sitting, watching movies, playing on the computer, or sitting. As we all know, physical education and sports are extremely important for physical and mental development and emotional mood. Exercises tailored to individual physical condition and age increase endurance, increase resistance to disease, and promote a sense of well-being. In addition, physical training is important in the treatment of cardiovascular diseases as well as obesity caused by hypodynamia.

Under the influence of physical exercise, oxidation processes increase, especially the role of enzymes in the working muscle system is activated, under the influence of more oxygen (O₂), the use of oxygen by tissues increases, and metabolic processes in the body improve. Physical exercises increase blood flow to the heart, expand blood vessels, and improve the nutrition of working capillaries. In obesity, deep breathing is also important. Develops diaphragmatic breathing during exercise. If obese patients regularly do physical exercises, the function of external respiration improves, more oxygen enters the body, and the activity of oxidation processes increases. All this helps the patient to better approach various physical loads. Therapeutic exercise activates oxidation-reduction processes, increases fat breakdown, and reduces excess body weight. Therapeutic exercises are given to the large muscles of the body in obesity. Therapeutic physical exercises can be used in the following forms. For example, morning hygienic gymnastics can be done in the form of 15-20 minutes of walking, various sports (volleyball, badminton, tennis), tourism, running. When used correctly with other activities, exercise provides relief to the body as well as being a powerful factor in preventing the accumulation of fillers in the body.

In conclusion, it can be said that doing physical education and sports, following a diet, and properly organizing the daily routine are important factors for human health, and every person needs to use them wisely in his daily life. formation is important.

Hypodynamia is a weakening of the body's muscle activity caused by a sedentary lifestyle, and although it is not considered a disease that has a negative impact on human health, it is the cause of rapid aging and premature death of millions of people. According to the "Orthodox" medical portal, hypodynamia surpasses even smoking as a cause of death: 5.3 million people die from hypodynamia, and 5 million people die from smoking. These are statistical studies conducted by scientists, and this indicator is based on only one year's data.

According to the UN News Center, two-thirds of the adult population suffers from a lack of physical activity. It should not be forgotten that serious diseases begin to develop in people who follow this lifestyle. Today, the rational use of health-promoting factors of physical education, which is important for human health, is equally important for people of all ages. It should be noted that many people of different ages have suffered as a result of the corona virus infection all over the world. We have realized that it depends on actions. A person should always be in motion, should not stop from activity, should be familiar with healthy activities after the mental cocktail. As we all know, there is a saying among our people that it is natural for a person who stops moving to sit, and for a person who is sitting to lie down, and for a person who is lying down to sleep. Therefore, we should always be physically active, which is the foundation of our healthy lifestyle, for our health and the future and health of our children. After all, it is not for nothing that it is said that the future of a country whose children are healthy will be great.

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